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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of Sol2H2O¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D5.1 - Relevant Impact Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

Given the nature of these plans, adaptations and/or changes are expected along the course of the project, befitting the objectives of assuring project dissemination, exploitation and communication. The most recent versions of documents and tools, supported by due log of changes/decisions, are made available on the project folder.

Changes to this deliverable, if needed, will be described and requested to the (PO) for resubmission of a later version of this document.

2. SOL2H2O WIDENING IMPACTS

Following the project objectives of raising UEvora Widening profile:

“Engaging three top-class leading partners around a scientific strategy for stepping up and stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity on Solar-driven Water-Energy Nexus solutions, Sol2H2O aims at enhanced networking with the Coordinator Widening partner, raising its research profile through the exploitation of their staff and infrastructural synergies in the establishment of a reference European facility for the development and testing of Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment technologies.”

Upon implementation of coordination and support measures aiming at the achievement, by the Widening institution (UEvora) of the 4CWC: Excellence Research, Attractive Careers, Aligned Strategy and Relevant Impact, the vision of SOL2H2O “Widening impacts” (WI’s) comprises:

- **WI.1:** EMSP @ UEvora delivers world-class research results in the field of Solar-driven Water-Energy Nexus solutions;
- **WI.2:** UEvora staff and structure present improved technical and administrative skills, enabling a more efficient research management encompassing state-of-the-art procedures adapted to its context;
- **WI.3:** UEvora is able to attract and retain Young Researchers at both the national and international levels;
- **WI.4:** UEvora integrates the most important international research fora and is acknowledged as an important partner by Industry;
- **WI.5:** UEvora research reaches 4Helix actors, is protected, accessible and exploited.

¹ Project: 101079305 — Sol2H2O — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

2.1. EMSP @ UEvora delivers world-class research

The research group of the Chair of Renewable Energy at the University of Évora (UEvora-CER) is dedicated to promoting innovative scientific research in the specific area of circular solar-powered water production and treatment technologies (WI.1). A research team at UEvora-CER actively conducts cutting-edge studies to advance the state of the art (SoA) in this field. The group's work focuses on the development and optimization of solar technologies for zero-liquid discharge desalination and brine material recovery, as well as solar photocatalysis technologies, with a particular focus on their applications in wastewater treatment. By integrating applied research with innovative technological development, UEvora-CER fosters a research environment geared toward scientific breakthroughs that address critical challenges in the water-energy nexus. The team's research activities are structured around the Joint Research Activity (JRA), which facilitates the coordinated participation of Senior Researchers (SRs), Young Researchers (YRs), and Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs), thus fostering the creation of a talent pipeline in the field. This approach not only strengthens research capacity but also promotes the development of early-career scientists through training and mentoring aligned with the project's objectives. The Joint Research Activity (JRA) currently includes one Senior Researcher (SR), one Young Researcher (YRs), and three Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs). Dedicated teams, composed of YR and CYR staff, have been assigned and have successfully completed tasks T2.1 and T2.2, relating to solar-powered water production and zero-liquid discharge desalination solutions, and solar-driven wastewater treatment, respectively. In addition, a comprehensive concept for an SoA and Beyond SoA has been developed and is formally documented in Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1). This Beyond SoA concept is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SOL2H2O “Beyond SoA” process flow scheme.

The development of the Widening RI represents a crucial initiative to expand capabilities in Circular Solar Water Production and Treatment technologies. The objective is to demonstrate a

technological combination that goes “beyond the state of the art”, surpassing the produced water recovery rate of current systems, which is around 50%, to reach levels close to 80%. This initiative is documented in a comprehensive R&D report that specifies the bill of materials and technical requirements of the facility. The actions, following the technical assessment derived from Task 2.1, included the design, construction, and commissioning of the heat and power interfaces of the existing Widening RI for the subsequent coupling of a treatment chain, as reported in Deliverable 2.2. The goal is to treat 1 cubic meter of water per day, and the facility is a sequential hybrid system consisting of a reverse osmosis (PVRO) system, a multi-feed plug-in flow reactor (MF-PFR), a membrane distillation (MD) system, and, in the final treatment stage, two solar evaporation ponds.

This "beyond SoA facility" supports the development of the resulting project proposals, contributing to raising UEvora's research profile through cutting-edge research (SOL2H2O Objective 1) by upgrading the Widening RI (KPI 1.2) and participating in more R&D project proposals (KPI 1.3), enabling an enhanced scope of research and services and the development of new research avenues.

Table 1 details the significant progress achieved toward Widening Impact 1 (WI.1), which highlights both the successful mobilization of human resources and the strategic advancement of the research infrastructure (RI). Key status indicators confirm that UEvora has established a devoted research team, with 1 Senior Researcher (SR), 1 Young Researcher (YR), and 3 Candidate Young Researchers (CYR) actively engaged in the Joint Research Activity (JRA) and has successfully defined specialized teams to tackle specific technical tasks (T2.1 and T2.2). Furthermore, RI upgrade activities are achieved, including the definition of the necessary intervention, materials lists, and engineering work, following the successful development of the State-of-the-Art (SoA) and beyond-SoA concepts (D2.1). These actions lay a solid foundation for accelerating applied research in Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment technologies.

Table 1. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 1 (WI.1): Delivering World-Class Research in Solar-driven Water-Energy Nexus solutions.

WI.1: EMSP @ UEvora delivers world-class research results in the field of Circular, Solar-driven Water-Production and Water Treatment technologies		
Description	Pathway	Status
UEvora-CER has a devoted team developing cutting-edge research on Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment technologies	Engagement of UEvora SR (Senior), YR (Young) and CYR (Candidate Young Researcher) in the JRA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 UEvora SR, 1 YR and 3 CYR are engaged in the JRA; 1 SR + 2 CYR team has been defined to tackle T2.1, and 1 YR + 1 CYR is being defined to tackle T2.2 - Further engagement of CYR and YR has been achieved among TOP partners (8 CYR + 4 YR)
UEvora RI enables the development of applied research aiming at the further development of Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment technologies and their further applications	Development of the JRA (WP2), including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment technologies	- A SoA and beyond SoA concept have been developed in T2.1 and T2.2 (D2.1); RI upgrade activities are finished, and the commissioning is done.

2.2. UEvora staff and structure present improved technical and administrative skills

UEvora is strengthening the technical and administrative capacities of its staff and organizational structures to ensure more efficient and effective research management, tailored to its specific context (WI.2). This improvement is achieved by streamlining project management procedures that integrate existing general management tools, such as financial execution tracking and timesheet registries, into comprehensive project execution control processes, including technical oversight and Gantt chart monitoring. A key aspect of this pathway is the integration of procurement-based purchasing and contracting procedures into an internal UEvora platform, which facilitates continuous monitoring of administrative workflows, automatic process alerts, and estimated completion times. The involvement of UEvora's Science and Cooperation Service (SCC) in project coordination activities ensures dedicated oversight and optimized management. Furthermore, dedicated project management workshops provided essential training to staff, fostering a shared understanding of best practices.

Particularly, to enhance operational efficiency and strategic output, a new management tool has been successfully adapted and implemented (OpenProject tool, Figure 2). This has been complemented by the development and implementation of new purchasing procedures to ensure a more streamlined and transparent process.

The project's commitment to excellence is demonstrated through the application of Quality and Risk Management tools, fully aligned with the PM² methodology. The artifacts of the PM² methodology and their implementation in the SOL2H2O project are shown in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. All Dissemination, Operation, and Communication (DEC) activities are now overseen by a dedicated Communications Manager, ensuring effective dissemination and impact dissemination.

Figure 2. SOL2H2O project in OpenProject platform.

Figure 3. PM2 Artifacts in SOL2H2O project for Communication Management Plan and Deliverables Acceptance Plan.

<This checklist should be reviewed and customised (if needed), when planning quality. The main purpose of the Quality Review Checklist is to support the Project Quality Reviewers when verifying (if key project activities were performed as

Project Quality Review	
Organisation / Department:	University of Évora / Renewable Energies Chair
Project Name:	SOL2H2O
Project Owner:	European Commission
Business Manager:	Constanza Conte
Solution Provider:	University of Évora
Project Manager:	Pedro Horta
Project Quality Reviewer:	UEVORA - SCC
Review Date:	16.02.2023
Overall Score:	94%
Overall Project Quality Assessment	0.94

Area	% of Quality Compliance	Score	Included?
Scope	96%	96%	Yes
Schedule	88%	88%	Yes
Cost	89%	89%	Yes
Quality	97%	97%	Yes
Risk	90%	90%	Yes
Issues & Decisions	94%	94%	Yes
Communication	100%	100%	Yes
Project Organisation	93%	93%	Yes
Outsourcing	100%	100%	Yes
Client Satisfaction	97%	97%	Yes

Project Quality Review	
Scope	96%
Schedule	88%
Cost	89%
Quality	97%
Risk	90%
Issues & Decisions	94%
Communication	100%
Project Organisation	93%
Outsourcing	100%
Client Satisfaction	97%

ID	Risk Identification and Description		Description	Related Task	Status	Identified By	Identification Date	Likelihood (L) 5-Very high, ..., 1-Very low	Impact (I) 5-Very high, ..., 1-Very low	Risk Level (L*I)	Risk Owner	Escalation	SUTABLE RESPONSE			
	Category	Title											Avoid	Reduce	Accept	Transfer/Share
RI.01	People & Organisation	Loss of key personnel	Loss of key personnel in the project management structure.	T1.1: Project Management	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	3	9	PM	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.02	People & Organisation	Faulty coordination.	Lack of coordination between partners.	T1.1: Project Management	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	3	6	PSC	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.03	External or Legal	Travel restrictions	Covid-19 pandemic not allowing for travelling.	T1.1: Project Management	Rejected	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	2	6	PM	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.04	Infrastructure	RI upgrade not viable.	RI upgrade implementation on EMSP HPS2-loop technically not possible.	T2.3: Widening upgrade	Rejected	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	3	6	PCT (WP2)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.05	External or Legal	FT School attendance	Fast-Track Schools have no registered attendants.	T3.1: Training	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	4	8	PCT (WP3)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.06	Adhesion	CYR engagement	A 2nd CYR is not identified by M10.	T3.2: Tutoring	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	4	12	PM	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.07	Adhesion	Living Amenities	Living Amenities pass has no subscriptions	T3.3: Living Activities	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	2	6	PCT (WP3)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.08	Adhesion	RSFora	Lack of interest in participation in RSFora	T4.1: Policy alignment	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	3	6	PCT (WP4)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.09	Adhesion	ESSymp and ETSymp	Lack of key stakeholder engagement in ESSymp and ETSymp.	T4.3: Industry engagement	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	3	6	PCT (WP4)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.10	Communication	Visibility	Lack of public visibility of project achievements and result	T5.2: DEC Activities	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	3	9	PCT (WP5)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.11	Infrastructure	RI upgrade not viable.	RI upgrade implementation on PECS-loop technically not possible.	T2.3: Widening upgrade	Closed	Consortium	2023-07-06	2	3	6	PCT (WP2)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.12	Infrastructure	Overall pilot components not available in time	Some pilot components can not be supplied in time for the commissioning of the pilot plant	T2.3: Widening upgrade	Closed	WP2 leader	2023-07-06	2	4	8	PCT (WP2)	Y	0	0	0	0
RI.13	People & Organisation	Unability to travel by	Due to different internal responsibilities and organigram,	T1.3: Widening	Closed	WP3 leader	2024-01-11	4	2	8	PCT (WP1)	N	0	0	0	0
RI.14	External or Legal	Data access limitations	Access to some assets of the facility is hampered by data access limitations due to confidentiality or similar reasons	T2.4: Distributed Facility	Approved	Phio	2025/06/19	2	3	6	UEVORA	N	0	0	0	0
RI.15	Adhesion	Contents for D1.5 are missing	D1.5: assessment of profile raising results from TOP partners are not available.	T1.3: Widening Profile	Approved	Phio	2025/06/19	2	1	2	PSC	N	0	0	0	0

Figure 4. PM2 methodology implemented in the SOL2H2O project for the Quality review checklist and Risk review.

According to the SheFigures 2024 report, despite notable progress, significant efforts are still required to achieve full gender equality (GE) across the European Union, including in Spain, Italy, and Portugal, countries included in the SOL2H2O consortium. In response, SOL2H2O implemented a series of targeted activities to promote GE, including initiatives to improve work-life balance, leadership training programs, and awareness-raising seminars. Survey results revealed limited awareness of existing institutional measures regarding GE, suggesting a need for improved communication and more effective implementation. The project also addressed persistent gender imbalances in leadership positions, structural barriers to women's career advancement, and the integration of the gender dimension in research and teaching. Furthermore, measures to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment were identified as essential, particularly to improve reporting procedures and institutional responses. Overall, the activities carried out within the framework of the SOL2H2O project fostered inclusive dialogue, strengthened institutional awareness, and led to concrete proposals for promoting gender equality in the participating organizations.

In addition, several strategic initiatives have been launched to foster an inclusive environment. These include implementing gender equality initiatives, organizing informational seminars, and distributing questionnaires. The institution has also successfully organized several regional (Regional Specialization Forums), national (Water-Energy Strategy Symposium), and international (Water-Energy Transition Symposium) events, and has invested in professional development through specialized leadership training (Figure 5). Thanks to these combined measures, UEvora has significantly improved its technical and administrative capacities, ensuring adaptation to the most advanced procedures and increasing overall institutional efficiency.

Figure 5. Leadership training held by UEvora.

Table 2 summarizes the substantial progress made toward Widening Impact 2 (WI.2), which aims to enhance UEvora's technical and administrative skills and structures to ensure more efficient research management. This impact is critical to adapting cutting-edge procedures to the university's specific context.

Key progress indicators confirm that UEvora has successfully focused on the integration of advanced management tools. The PM2 methodology was presented during the Kick-Off Meeting (KoM), and a comprehensive PM2-based project management framework (D1.1) has since been implemented, supported by a dedicated Technical and Administrative Staff (TADM) collaborator working directly on management and Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities. Furthermore, to optimize administrative workflows, UEvora has focused on procurement: an experimental procurement platform is currently operational within the research group, and one of its core functionalities has already been successfully transferred to the centralized institutional system. These steps mark a significant advance toward the institutionalization of efficient and modern research management practices.

Table 2. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 2 (WI.2): Enhancing Research Management Skills and Efficiency.

WI.2: UEvora staff and structure present improved technical and administrative skills enabling a more efficient research management encompassing state-of-the-art procedures adapted to its context		
Description	Pathway	Status
UEvora project management procedures are enhanced and integrate already existing general management tools (financial execution, timesheet registry) into project execution control procedures (technical execution, Gantt monitoring)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UEvora-SCC are engaged in Project Coordination activities - Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UEvora-SCC services have a detached TADM collaborator working in the project management and DEC activities - PM2 methodology has been presented along with KoM, and a PM2-based project management framework has been implemented (D1.1)
Public procurement-based purchasing and hiring procedures are integrated into the internal UEvora platform, enabling monitoring of the administrative process, process alerts and estimated conclusion	Development of an internal purchasing platform	- An experimental purchasing platform has been developed and is in use in the research group; one functionality has been passed to the centralized system

2.3. UEvora is able to attract and retain Young Researchers

UEvora highlights its successful ability to attract and retain Young Researchers (YRs) both nationally and internationally, fostering a dynamic research community within the SOL2H2O framework (WI.3). At UEvora, YRs are trained to become leading experts in their respective fields, often assuming leadership roles by leading research teams dedicated to SOL2H2O topics. Candidate Young Researchers (CYR) approaching the completion of their doctoral studies are fully integrated into the UEvora research environment, with clear pathways to transition to YR positions. The institution also attracts international CYRs whose doctoral research aligns closely with the Joint Research Activity (JRA). Participation in JRA is enhanced through access to specific training and mentoring programs, offered in collaboration with TOP partners and Research Infrastructures (RIs), including participation in SOL2H2O Fast-Track Schools, which provide key expertise and foster international networking. Professional development is actively supported. Furthermore, the attractiveness of living in Évora, combined with dedicated Living Amenities and mentoring initiatives, creates a supportive environment that encourages permanence and personal development. These joint efforts ensure a dynamic and sustainable flow of talented researchers who contribute significantly to the research excellence of UÉvora.

UEvora's Young Researcher (YR) has established herself as a leading researcher in the SOL2H2O field and is fully engaged in the development of the Joint Research Activity (JRA). This researcher leads a devoted team in these topics and is provided with access to training and mentoring from TOP partners and TOP RIs. Concurrently, the CYRs at UEvora are approaching the completion of their PhD research. The objective is for these individuals to become YRs and be integrated into the dedicated UEvora team. Their PhD theses are closely aligned with the SOL2H2O JRA, and they benefit from training and tutoring provided by TOP partners and TOP RIs. The SOL2H2O Fast-Track Schools serve a critical function by delivering specialized know-how and engaging an international audience of both YRs and CYRs.

In the framework of the SOL2H2O project, two key initiatives have been implemented to support the professional growth of researchers: Tutoring and Mentoring. The tutoring program is designed to support Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs) in the development of their PhD theses, facilitating a total of 11.64 weeks of mobility for CYRs from UEvora to TOP partners, UNIPA, ITC and CIEMAT. The mentoring initiative, conversely, is aimed at the career development of Young Researchers (YRs) who are engaged in the project, with the specific goal of preparing them for future leadership roles in the SOL2H2O field. A satisfaction survey conducted from October 2024 until August 2025, with responses from eight CYRs and YRs, indicated high levels of satisfaction with the project. The team satisfaction was rated at an average of 4.88 out of 5, while the general satisfaction with SOL2H2O received an average rating of 4.63. Additionally, to further support career progression towards leadership positions, a dedicated leadership training program was held for the UEvora team, including both YRs and CYRs, in May 2025.

In alignment with SOL2H2O's objective to foster the career advancement of Young Researchers (YRs), targeted support has been provided for the preparation and submission of proposals to the ERC Starting Grant scheme, one of the most competitive and prestigious funding instruments in the European research landscape, aimed at researchers with 2 to 7 years of postdoctoral experience. Limitations on the eligibility requirements amongst the Consortium's YR meant that only one proposal was submitted by Nunzio Cancilla from UNIPA in the scope of SOL2H2O project: "Greenhouse Renewable Energy and Environmental Nexus with Water-from-Air Technology for Efficient Resources – GREENWATER". Although the proposal was not selected to proceed to the second evaluation stage, it provided valuable experience in ERC proposal development. Regarding a Synergy grant, as the consortium is working with too high TRL levels, it was decided that it was better to reorient the efforts toward higher TRL call proposals, and a proposal for the PRIMA call was submitted. Nevertheless, YRs in the project benefited from the proposal facility developed. In this framework, they were instrumental in the presentation of two European proposals (Innovation Activities in the call HORIZON-CL6-2024-CIRCBIO-02 (Circular economy and bioeconomy sectors, topic:

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CircBio-02-4-two-stage), two regional proposals and one international proposal (the aforementioned to the PRIMA call).

The PhD programs developed within the framework of the Joint Research Activity (JRA) are centered on Circular Solar-driven Water Production and Water Treatment technologies. Seven specific PhD programs have been delineated, five of which are currently underway. Aligned with JRA task 2.1 are:

- The "Optimizing Solar-driven Water Production and Brine Valorization for Sustainable Solutions" program, focused on developing efficient and environmentally friendly systems for solar-driven water production, including Photovoltaic powered - Reverse Osmosis (PV-RO) desalination and Solar-powered Vacuum-enhanced air-gap Membrane Distillation, as well as exploring innovative approaches for brine valorization through solar ponds to extract valuable salts while minimizing environmental impact.
- The "Viability and applicability of SWRO brine valorisation processes in the Canary Islands" program, focused on proposing processes for seawater brine valorisation in the Canary Islands from a circular economy perspective and to present the feasibility and applicability of these processes from an industrial standpoint.
- The "Batch operating solar membrane distillation systems for concentration of brines" program, already completed, focused on the characterization, modelling and optimization of a solar membrane distillation system and its operation in recirculation for brine concentration.
- The "Valorization of seawater waste brines by recovering trace element", already completed, focused on analyzing a possible treatment chain for bitterns to recover all the elements of interest using a circular approach with low environmental impact.
- The "Innovative processes for brine valorization" program, focused on developing strategies for the valorization of waste brines, by the recovery of minerals (such as magnesium) and the production of drinking water.

Aligned with JRA task 2.2 are:

- The " Industrial wastewater regeneration and recovery of added-value substances", focused on the reduction of the water footprint related to the industry through the integration of technologies for the treatment and regeneration of industrial and/or complex wastewater and the recovery of nutrients or added-value substances contained in such wastewaters.
- The " Wastewater treatment by solar photocatalysis" program is focused on the application of solar reactors for the decontamination and disinfection of wastewater.

CYR (Candidate Young Researchers) and YR (Young Researchers) were among the main target groups of the Fast-Track Schools (FTS), which were designed as progressive training sessions throughout the SOL2H2O project. The FTS aimed to provide CYR and YR, as well as industry engineers and technicians, with advanced knowledge and hands-on experience in key areas of solar-driven water production & treatment technologies and brine treatment processes. The training evolved over three editions, covering:

- Introduction to solar-driven water production & treatment technologies and brine treatment processes. State of the Art. (Palermo, January 2024),
- Beyond State of the Art in solar-driven water production & treatment technologies and brine treatment processes (Pozo Izquierdo, September 2024),
- Technology benchmarking and exploitation strategies (Évora, February 2025).

These schools (Figure 6) helped to develop technical skills and project-relevant expertise for CYRs and YRs, enhancing their professional growth and preparing them to contribute actively to the project's goals.

Figure 6. The three editions of the FTS.

The original concept for a "Living Amenities Pass" was conceived to assist new researchers with integration into the local community. However, its implementation faced significant legal and administrative obstacles, particularly concerning financial management and public procurement regulations. As a result, the project consortium adopted a revised approach, pivoting from the pass to a new, two-part solution. The first component is an expanded "Living in..." section on the project website (Figure 7), which provides newcomers with a comprehensive set of resources, including a map of key points of interest, a calendar of local events, videos, and useful contacts related to the Alentejo, Sicily and Gran Canaria regions. The second and more significant component is the "Mentoring Initiative" (Figure 8). This program pairs new researchers, referred to as "mentees," with volunteer "mentors" from the UEvora's research and technical staff. The mentors' role is to provide practical assistance with non-work-related matters, such as finding accommodation and navigating administrative processes, thereby facilitating the mentees' successful integration into the city and region.

Figure 7. "Living in..." on the SOL2H2O website.

Figure 8. “Mentoring Program” on the SOL2H2O website.

Table 3 indicates the key status achieved toward Widening Impact 3 (WI.3), which focuses on UEvora’s ability to attract and retain Young Researchers (YR) at both national and international levels. This impact is central to building a sustainable, high-quality research team.

The data confirms significant success in engaging and developing talent. A YR is fully engaged in the Joint Research Activity (JRA) across task T2.2, with tangible career development pathways established: the YR defined mentoring arrangements with top partners, have completed mobility periods in the TOP Research Infrastructures (RI). Similarly, Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs) are being successfully integrated: all 3 CYRs are developing PhD theses aligned with the JRA topics and have attended the Fast-Track School. Finally, UEvora has enhanced its external appeal by implementing the Mentoring Program as an alternative to Living Amenities, making the location more attractive, serviceable and enjoyable to both national and international researchers.

Table 3. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 3 (WI.3): Attraction and Retention of Young Researchers.

WI.3: UEvora is able to attract and retain Young Researchers at both national and international level		
Description	Pathway	Status
UEvora YR becomes a leading researcher in the SOL2H2O research field, leading a devoted team in these topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - YR fully engaged in the development of the JRA - YR has access to Training and Mentoring activities with TOP partners and TOP RI - YR career development through an ERC proposal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 YR engaged in the development of the JRA, along with T2.2 topics - 2 CYR engaged in the development of the JRA, along with T2.1 topics - 1 YR and 3 CYR have attended FTSchools and provided contents; 1 YR and 2 CYR have had mobility in 3 TOP RI; 1 CYR has had mobility in 2 TOP RI; 1 YR have defined mentoring by TOP partners - ERC proposal calls identified and 1 eligible

		YR identified in one TOP partner - 1 ERC Starting Grant proposal submitted
- UEvora CYR is close to the completion of the PhD research and aims to become a YR integrated in the UEvora devoted team - UEvora is able to attract an international CYR developing a PhD integrated and aligned with SOL2H2O JRA	- CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with (a) SOL2H2O JRA and have access to Training and Tutoring with TOP partners and TOP RI (b) SOL2H2O Fast-Track Schools deliver know-how and engage an international audience of YR and CYR	3 CYR are developing PhD thesis aligned with JRA in T2.1 and T2.2
Living in Évora is attractive to national and international YR and CYR	Living Amenities facility	Living Amenities contents implemented in the SOL2H2O website; Alternative to pass implemented.

2.4. UEvora integrates the most important international research fora and is acknowledged as an important partner by Industry

UEvora's efforts led to its integration into water-related key international research fora and its recognition as a valuable partner by industry stakeholders (WI.4), demonstrating its commitment to contributing to cutting-edge research and innovation. The university has enhanced its networking profile by engaging with the most relevant Scientific and Industry fora: European Desalination Society - EDS, the European Technology Platform Water Europe - WE, and the Water4All Partnership - Water Security for the planet, namely, through the cooperation in the organization of the Water4All 360° Water Experience Tour for Bachelor students. Furthermore, UÉvora also participates in the IEA-SHC Task 72 | Solar Photoreactors for the Production of Fuels and Chemicals. The collaboration with industry is strengthened through joint research activities conducted within the Widening Research Infrastructure, facilitating direct knowledge transfer and co-development of innovative solutions. This multifaceted engagement is supported by a dedicated proposal facility, aimed at securing funding to sustain and expand these collaborative efforts. Collectively, these initiatives position UEvora as a key player at the intersection of research excellence and industry relevance on both national and international stages.

Table 4. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 4 (WI.4): International Networking and Industrial Partnership.

WI.4: UEvora integrates the most important international research fora and is acknowledged as an important partner by Industry		
Description	Pathway	Status
UEvora presents an updated and upgraded profile of participation in IEA-SHC Task 62	- UEvora participation extended to Solar-driven WP technologies - UEvora applies for a Portuguese representation in Water Europe and for EDS membership	- Activities in IEA-SHC Task 62 were stopped when the SOL2H2O project started, however, it currently integrates the IEA-SHC Task 72 Solar Photoreactors for the Production of Fuels and Chemicals;

		- Formal participation of UEvora in EDS and Water Europe achieved
- UEvora engages Industrial partners in joint research activities in the Widening RI - UEvora provides R&D services to Industrial partner under a service contract	Proposal Facility	- A PM2 based proposal writing support tool has been developed and is in use; 5 EU proposals, and 2 Regional proposals have been submitted

2.5. UEvora research reaches 4Helix actors

UEvora ensures the broad dissemination, protection, accessibility, and exploitation of its research within the 4Helix innovation model, which encompasses academia, industry, policymakers, and civil society (WI.5). Research outputs from UEvora’s Research Infrastructure (RI) and Joint Research Activity (JRA) are consistently presented in peer-reviewed journals and major scientific conferences, such as EDS organized conferences and ISES, ensuring visibility and validation within the global scientific community. The impact of SOL2H2O research is explicitly aligned with the ongoing energy transition and correlates strongly with national and regional industrial strategies and specialization agendas, fostering clear relevance to academic, policy, and industrial stakeholders alike. To safeguard innovations and maximize their commercial potential, UEvora has developed a robust Intellectual Property (IP) protection framework and a comprehensive Commercial Exploitation Plan, formalized through a “Spin-off Blueprint” that guides the creation of new companies. Additionally, UEvora researchers and staff maintain close integration with local actors, facilitating contextualized knowledge transfer and regional development. This comprehensive approach is further supported by dedicated events such as the SOL2H2O Water Energy Transition Symposium and Regional Specialization Forum, alongside the provision of Living Amenities, which collectively strengthen community engagement and ensure research output effectively contributes to sustainable innovation ecosystems.

One of the main objectives of the SOL2H2O project’s dissemination strategy was to ensure the publication of scientific results in peer-reviewed, open-access journals whenever possible. By the end of the project, nine peer-reviewed articles had been published, and four are foreseen to be submitted. Additionally, over two other scientific contributions were produced within the scope of SOL2H2O, although they do not formally acknowledge the project. All eligible publications, along with their associated datasets and metadata, were deposited in Zenodo, in alignment with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. Zenodo was chosen over alternative repositories such as OpenAIRE for its seamless functionality, data hosting flexibility, and strong commitment to long-term preservation, backed by CERN and the European OpenAIRE programme. A complete list of publications, including DOIs and repository links, is available in deliverable D5.2 Final Report on DEC.

In support of SOL2H2O’s objective to strengthen the networking of UEvora within scientific and industrial forums, a series of strategic activities were conducted, including the Regional Specialization Fora, the Water Energy Strategy Symposium, and the Water Energy Transition Symposium. The Regional Specialization Fora were foreseen to take place every 6 months, with a total of 5 events along the project, in M6, M12, M18, M24 and M30. Due to technical-administrative constraints, the first RSF was organised in M11, and 4 editions have already been held (RSF#4 was held together with the Water-Energy Strategy Symposium to promote more participation of regional actors). Beyond the foreseen Regional Specialization Fora at the Widening partner’s location, in view of the pressing interest in alternative water resources in Sicily, an additional RSF edition took place in Palermo, in April’24.

With the first edition dedicated to presenting the project’s scope and technological solutions, these Fora fostered an ongoing debate with participants about the potential of Sol2H2O

technologies for the region, the role that regional industry could play in their development, and the potential impact of both technology use and production on the RIS3 and the regional development strategy.

While the number of attendees increased with each RSF event, the lack of regional players in the Sol2H2O technology field became evident. Indeed, as this is an essentially agricultural region, with the exception of some existing industrial capacities in the region's only relevant industrial hub—the Sines petrochemical complex—that develop activities and offer expertise not directly related to the scope of the JRA Sol2H2O, the success of these initiatives, measured by the target audience to which the proposal was directed, proved to be modest.

The Water-Energy Strategy Symposium attracted stakeholders from academia, policymakers, and industry. One of the topics that sparked particular interest among the audience was the coverage of the Sol2H2O Beyond SoA technology value chain, both regionally and nationally. Important conclusions were drawn from this. At the regional level, existing companies can only cover Sol2H2O-related value chains by 19% for installation activities, 40% for operation and maintenance activities, and no capabilities are found for manufacturing activities. At the national level, these figures rise to 59% for manufacturing and 100% for both installation and operation and maintenance. This study demonstrated that the involvement of industrial stakeholders around Sol2H2O technology solutions is likely to benefit from a nationwide collaboration. Following this conclusion and audience feedback, a second nationwide collaboration was organized in Porto, where the 2024 Conference of the European Desalination Society took place. The discussion focused on the possibility of creating a Partnership for Desalination and Wastewater Reuse: Alternative Water Resources, which generated clear interest among attendees. Following this meeting, another one was held in Évora (July 11) to continue the debate on the creation of a Portuguese association for alternative water resources, and to define: (i) Mission; (ii) Objectives; (iii) Lines of action; (iv) Management.

The Water-Energy Transition Symposium (WETSymp) was a two-day international symposium aimed at presenting and discussing the potential role of solar water production and treatment technologies and Water-Energy technologies in the objectives of the National Energy and Climate Plan, as well as the potential for industrial development and technology export resulting from the application of existing/under development industrial capacity to the technological solutions sought in Sol2H2O. This international symposium was developed in two stages: a national-level discussion in each of the consortium member countries (Portugal, Italy, and Spain) with a selected group of key stakeholders in this field, and an international-level discussion to compare the results of the different presentations. Led by industry stakeholders, this discussion allowed the Consortium not only to gain a broad overview of the most relevant approaches to the challenges identified in the stakeholder questions in each country, but also to extract a series of concrete actions for the subsequent promotion of Sol2H2O technological solutions and their market acceptance.

Figure 9. Water-Energy Strategy Symposium and Water-Energy Transition Symposium events.

In the framework of the SOL2H2O project, a Spin-Off Facility has been developed, dedicated to both YRs and CYRs (Figure 10). This initiative provided structured guidance on the creation of spin-off companies, including legal, financial, and fiscal aspects, as well as intellectual property protection strategies. Developed in collaboration with the Employability, Community and Cross-cutting Projects Division of the University of Évora (DECPT), the facility included seminars and practical materials covering the full innovation cycle—from ideation and validation to market entry and investor engagement. An "Innovation Assets Matrix" was also introduced to map and assess existing support resources within the Widening institution and partner organizations, with the aim of identifying gaps and fostering inter-consortium collaboration. A business model study is underway to explore the potential of operating the upgraded research facility (developed under WP2) as an independent service provider, serving as a practical blueprint for spin-off creation. Selected materials from the Spin-Off Facility will be made publicly available via the project’s Zenodo repository.

Figure 10. Exemplary contents of Spin-Off facility materials.

The original "Living Amenities Pass" aimed to help new researchers integrate locally but faced legal and administrative challenges. The project shifted to a two-part solution: an expanded "Living in Alentejo" website section offering key local resources, and a "Mentoring Initiative" pairing new researchers with University of Évora staff volunteers who assist with practical, non-work-related matters to ease their integration, as indicated in section 2.3.

The table below provides a concise summary of the progress achieved under Widening Impact 5 (WI.5), which is designed to ensure UEvora’s research is protected, accessible, and effectively exploited across the 4Helix actors (Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil society).

The status confirms successful execution across all dissemination and exploitation fronts. UEvora’s research output has been significantly amplified, evidenced by 7 scientific publications and active participation in multiple high-profile international conferences, including EDS and CIES. Furthermore, the project successfully enhanced strategic engagement with stakeholders by organizing and completing four Regional Specialization Forums by Month 27, alongside making content from the Water-Energy Strategy and Water-Energy Transition Symposia widely available. Finally, concerning exploitation, an Innovation and Entrepreneurship assets Matrix was developed, complementing the training sessions already delivered in multiple Project Management (ProM) workshops. These integrated activities ensure robust dissemination, clear IP protection planning, and strong local integration, supported by the implemented Living Amenities content and Mentoring program.

Table 5. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 5 (WI.5): Research Dissemination and Exploitation.

WI.5: UEvora research reaches 4Helix actors, is protected, accessible and exploited		
Description	Pathway	Status
UEvora RI and JRA are presented in peer-reviewed journals and Scientific Conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publication of articles in peer-reviewed Journals - Participation in EDS and ISES Conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 Publication published in peer-reviewed Journal; - Participation in EDS'24 and EDS'25 Conferences
SOL2H2O research impacts on Energy Transition and on the National and Regional Industrial and Specialization Strategies are clear to Academia, Policy and Industrial actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SOL2H2O Water-Energy Strategy Symposium - SOL2H2O Water-Energy Transition Symposium - SOL2H2O Regional Specialisation Forum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WESSymp contents available - WETSymp contents available - 4 editions of the RSForum took place by M31 in Évora and an edition took place in Palermo
SOL2H2O results exploitation encompasses a clear Intellectual Property Protection path and Commercial Exploitation Plan, embedded into a "Spin-off Blueprint"	Spin-Off "blueprint"	Innovation and Entrepreneurship contents and sessions already took place in ProM#3, ProM#4, ProM#5, and ProM#6; Innovation and Entrepreneurship assets Matrix developed
UEvora researchers and staff are fully integrated with the local actors and context	Living Amenities Facility	Living Amenities contents implemented in SOL2H2O website; Mentoring Initiative implemented

3. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Data Management Plan

The Deliverable 1.2 - DMP includes the project Data Management strategy and rules. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

The Deliverable 1.3 - DEC Plan includes the project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive in Google Drive. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A and B) <Grant Agreement-101079305-Sol2H2O-1.pdf>	Project folder
3	D1.2 Data Management Plan <SOL2H2O_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLAN_15-05-2023_v_2>	Project folder
4	D1.3 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan <SOL2H2O_D_1_3_DEC_PLAN_25-09-2023_v_3>	Project folder
5	D4.1 Regional, National and International Fora Report <SOL2H2O_D_4_1_Regional, National and International Fora Report_01-07-2025_v_1>	Project folder
6	Deliverables acceptance plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder
7	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder